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Design, Structuration and Rheological Properties of Laponite based Polymeric Nanocomposites

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Nanocomposites

- **Dispersion of a few percent of nanoscale particles into polymer matrix \Rightarrow improved polymer properties**
 - Mechanical properties
 - Barrier properties
 - Thermal endurance
 - Improved electrical, electronic properties
- **First patents in the beginning of 90's by Toyota**
 - Incorporation of clay platelets in PA

Key questions with nanocomposites

- **How to disperse the particles at the individual scale ?**
 - Create specific interactions between particles and polymer
 - ✓ Surface treatment of the particles
 - How to mix polymer and particles ?
 - ✓ Direct mixing or master batch
- **How are the properties linked to the state of dispersion ?**
 - Interest for properties in the molten state

Aim of the work

- **Establish relationships between rheological properties in the molten state and dispersion state of the particles**
 - Use of a well defined (model) system.
 - Study influence of preparation procedure to vary the dispersion.
 - Enlarge to other systems.

- **Small angle X-ray used to measure the dispersion state of the particle.**

- **The direct visualization of internal structure was conducted using Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM) and Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM).**

Model nanocomposites based on Laponite and PEO

Laponite

- Laponite : synthetic smectic clay that belongs to the structural family known as 2:1 phyllosilicate.
- Laponite : nanometric disk-like particles with numerous negative charges on the faces and some positive charges at the edges at the origin of slow aggregation in water media.

Protection of laponite particles

1) By adsorption of PEO chains

2) By grafting-PN 5k, 2k, 1k

Structure - Rheology relationships

- Matrix PEO10K; 6.5wt%; 80°C

Loiseau and Tassin, Macromolecules (2006)

Effect of preparation methods

Rheology : Influence of preparation

Laponite Protected by adsorbed chains
S-solution route; M-Melt route; T=110°C

Scaling Behavior

➤ Large change in the elastic filler network behavior depending on preparation methods.

Viscoelasticity-structure correlation

- Comparison of 1% nanocomposites from different concentration master batches

- Weak effect in SAXS – Strong effect in Rheology

Towards an explanation?

PEO/Laponite S- 10wt%

Dilution with PEO
10000 by Melt
procedure

PEO/Laponite (M- 1.0wt%) sample

PEO/Laponite S-3.5wt%

Dilution with PEO
10000 by Melt
procedure

PEO/Laponite (M-1.0wt%) sample

Polymer blends nanocomposites based on PMMA-PEO blends/Laponite

Motivations : extend the study from simple polymer nanocomposites to polymer blends nanocomposites

1) Preparation of polymer blends nanocomposites

- Nanocomposites based on PMMA-PEO blends and Laponite were prepared by a combination of solution mixing and melt dispersion procedures.

2) Miscibility of PMMA/PEO blend and their nanocomposites

- Miscibility of the blends and their nanocomposites has been studied using visual observation, X-ray diffraction, TEM and SEM.

a. Visual observation

b. X-ray diffraction

- Sample with the PMMA concentration higher than 70% are completely amorphous.
- Sample with the PMMA concentration less than 70% are completely crystalline.

c. SEM results

- PMMA/PEO blends up to 30wt% PEO appear quite homogeneous.
- When Laponite is added, the heterogeneity of the surface is increased.

f. TEM micrographs

- When adding Laponite, domains with a micron size appear
- Strong electron density due to the high concentration of Laponite particles.

3) Rheological properties

- Progressive change in the G' , G'' profile when PEO content increases
- Apparition of a low frequency plateau at 50% PEO and above

5) Effect of Laponite concentration

Rheology of amorphous blends

➤ No appearance of low frequency plateau.

DSC of amorphous blends

➤ T_g's do not seem much affected by the introduction of Laponite.

5) Effect of Laponite concentration

Rheology of Immiscible blends

➤ Appearance of low frequency plateau.

DSC of Immiscible blends

➤ Laponite inhibits the crystallization of PEO.

Towards an explanation?

- At high concentration of PEO in the blends :
 - existence of 2 phases
 - a continuous phase containing PEO and Laponite above percolation concentration

- At low concentration of PEO in the blends :
 - PEO diffuse to PMMA phase
 - Domain rich Laponite dispersed in matrix of PMMA/PEO (identical matrix)

Conclusions and perspectives

- Best state of dispersion as well highest moduli are obtained from solution prepared samples with high molecular weight of polymer matrix regardless of the way of protecting the particles.
- From rheological point of view PMMA/PEO blends nanocomposites behave as simple polymer nanocomposites at high concentration of PEO whereas deviated at low concentration of PEO.
- The optimum conditions with PEO/PMMA blends nanocomposites could be used to improve the conductivity of solid state batteries electrolyte since in some conditions the crystallinity of PEO can be kept low, leading to an increase in ion conductivity.

Thank you for your attention